

Supp. Figure 2. Percentage of total variance explained by each dimension obtained from the Factor Analysis of Mixed Data. The total variance in the sample among all variables measured can be summarized by independent dimensions, in this case dim 1-4 summarize ~85% of the total variance in the sample.

